

Respiratory health evaluation by leveraging lung surfactant fluid

Christie M. Sayes

Baylor University, USA

Abstract

Respiratory health is a critical component of human health. This physiological system allows gas exchange, activates defense mechanisms, detoxifies bioactive materials, and maintains pH. When the system is perturbed, the result is diminished lung capacity. The threshold levels that induce acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and actionable evidence that describes whether the health endpoints are reversible are mainly missing from chemical hazard assessments. In this talk, I will describe our standardized and systematic method to conduct aerosol-to-lung interaction studies in a stand-alone chamber capable of simulating occupational environments. The interaction studies were performed using two different models: the changes in lung surfactant fluid biophysical properties and perturbations in lung cell/tissue biochemical expressions.